

AWARENESS, ACCEPTABILITY, AND CONGRUENCY OF BOHOL ISLAND STATE UNIVERSITY'S VMGO

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Awareness, Acceptability, and Congruency of Bohol Island State University's VMGO

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Abstract

This study evaluates the levels of awareness, acceptability, and alignment of the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of Bohol Island State University (BISU) among its stakeholders. Data were collected using researcher-developed questionnaires administered to 644 randomly selected students, faculty, staff, and external stakeholders of the BISU Calape Campus. The study employed a descriptive research design, with data analysis conducted using means and other statistical tools. Results indicate that BISU's VMGO is effectively communicated and implemented, particularly in the areas of dissemination and awareness. However, there is a need for greater student involvement in the VMGO formulation and revision processes. Recommendations include enhancing the integration of the VMGO in educational practices to foster deeper engagement and alignment.

Keywords: *vision, mission, awareness, acceptability, congruency*

Introduction

In the field of higher education, the Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) of an institution serve as fundamental pillars that shape its strategic direction, define its core values, and express its commitment to stakeholders. Bohol Island State University (BISU), as a key academic institution in the Central Visayas region, relies heavily on its VMGO to promote academic quality, community involvement, and holistic student development. The effectiveness of these guiding principles is determined not only by their thoughtful formulation but also by how well they resonate with the expectations and perceptions of the university's stakeholders, including students, faculty, staff, and the surrounding community.

Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) serve as the foundation of any institution which set direction and as a fundamental guide to university's operations. An organization's VMGO are its lifeline to sustainable development –that is, being able to “meet the needs of the present without compromising the well-being of the future” (Pladson, 2011; Dungan, et al., 2016).

Bohol Island State University (BISU) is an educational institution governed by its vision, mission, goals and objectives which established the birth of the organization and of the aspiration for the future.

As per BOR Resolution No.59, Series of 2010, Revised and approved as part of BISU Strategic Plan 2012-2010, and BOR Resolution No. 60, Series of 2012, the vision states,

“BISU is a premiere Science and Technology University for the formation of a world-class and virtuous human resource for the sustainable development in Bohol and the country.”

Moreover, the University's mission as revised and approved as part of BISU Strategic Plan 2012-2020, and BOR Resolution No. 60, Series of 2012 states,

“BISU is committed to provide quality higher education in the arts and sciences, as well as in the professional and technological fields; undertake research and development, and extension services for the sustainable development of Bohol and the country.”

To deliver its mandate, BISU is directing all its efforts towards excellence guided by its foresight. To address the needs of the strategic sectors, BISU promote the following goals:

- O Pursue faculty and education excellence and strengthen the current viable curricular programs and develop curricular programs that are responsive to the demands of the times both in the industry and the environment;
- O Promote quality research outputs that respond to the needs of the local and national communities;
- O Develop communities through responsive extension programs;
- O Adopt efficient and profitable income generating projects/enterprise for self-sustainability;
- O Provide adequate, state-of-the-art and accessible infrastructure support facilities for quality education; and
- O Promote efficient and effective good governance supportive of high-quality education.

The awareness, acceptability, and congruency of Bohol Island State University's (BISU) Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) have been positively assessed among its stakeholders. A study conducted at BISU Clarin Campus revealed that 314 respondents, including students, faculty, staff, and parents, demonstrated a strong awareness and acceptability of the university's VMGO and grading system, indicating a favorable perception of these elements within the educational framework. While BISU stakeholders showed high awareness, the need for ongoing evaluations was highlighted to ensure sustained alignment with educational

practices and stakeholder expectations. A major recommendation is to conduct a parallel study may be conducted yearly to assess and monitor the stakeholders' awareness and acceptability of the VMGO and grading system of the different programs that the university offers. Overall, the findings suggest a robust foundation for BISU's VMGO, yet underscore the necessity for periodic reviews to adapt to evolving educational needs. (Batan, et.al., 2022). With this, the researcher felt the need to conduct this study. However, grading system is not included.

This aligns with findings from other institutions, such as Capiz State University, where stakeholders also exhibited high levels of awareness and acceptance of their VMGO, emphasizing the importance of continuous engagement and assessment to maintain this congruency (Joaquin, C. J. A., Besa, E. M. D., & Joaquin, H. D., 2023).

Furthermore, another study which determined the level of implementation of the VMGO of Bohol Island State University to the students, parents, cooperating agencies, and the community. The study specifically designed to evaluate the level of implementation of VMGO in terms of participation in the formulation or revision, dissemination, awareness, and integration. Questionnaires were distributed to 231 students and 93 parents from BISU Balilihan, 86 barangay officials in the municipality of Balilihan, and 90 representatives from cooperating agencies. Based on the findings, the level of implementation of VMGO is best implemented as perceived by the students. Otherwise, it is better implemented based on the findings from other groups of respondents. The researchers have concluded that students of the BISU-Balilihan Campus have a higher level of awareness and acceptability than the parents, community, and cooperating agencies (Tuico, Riame T., 2022).

BISU excels in different areas both in academe and technology. It has community outreach to different adapted barangays in the province of Bohol. In the course of assessing how responsive is the University's VMGO to the community needs, the researchers opted to conduct this study. This study seeks to investigate the awareness, acceptability and congruency of BISU's VMGO among its stakeholders.

The output of this study will serve as the starting point for developing a shared vision strategy to enhance the University's VMGO to make it more receptive to the community demands. The development of knowledge, technology and skills in the university is geared towards the improvement of the economic status of the community. The University's instruction, research and extension, and production programs are driven towards the fulfillment of its shared vision, mission, goals and objectives. It encompasses basic functional needs and demands designed to establish and promote the general well-being of the rural and urban populace.

Research Questions

The general objective of this study is to evaluate the implementation level of BISU's VMGO. Specifically, it aims to:

1. Assess the levels of awareness and implementation of BISU's VMGO in terms of stakeholder participation in its formulation, revision, dissemination, and integration into educational practices and activities.
2. Provide recommendations based on the study's findings to enhance the alignment and effectiveness of BISU's VMGO.

Methodology

Research Design

The conduct of the study follows the standard proceedings in data gathering employing the descriptive survey method aided by a questionnaire. To make the questions clear and understandable it was stated in two versions, English for the faculty and students and "Bisaya" for the community. The sample size of the respondents was determined through Slovin's formula employing proportionate cluster sampling and convenience sampling. The gathered data was treated using the frequency count and weighted mean.

Respondents

The respondents were the 644 randomly selected students of Bohol Island State University Calape Campus through stratified random sampling from the colleges and departments and to the faculty and staff as well as its external stakeholders.

Instrument

The study used a researcher-made questionnaire designed to capture data on the levels of awareness, acceptability, and congruency of BISU's VMGO.

Procedure

This study employed a structured research procedure to systematically evaluate the awareness, acceptability, and congruency of Bohol Island State University's (BISU) Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO) among its stakeholders. Initially, a researcher-developed questionnaire was created to serve as the primary data collection tool. The questionnaire was designed in both English and Bisaya to cater to the language preferences of the diverse participant groups, ensuring clarity and comprehension. The sample size, consisting of 644 participants including students, faculty, staff, and external stakeholders from BISU Calape Campus, was determined using Slovin's formula to achieve representativeness. Stratified random sampling was employed to ensure that all relevant stakeholder groups were adequately represented in the study.

Prior to full-scale data collection, the questionnaire was pre-tested with a small group of stakeholders to assess its clarity, relevance, and reliability. Feedback from this pre-test phase was used to refine the questions for better accuracy and effectiveness. Following this, data collection commenced with the administration of the questionnaires, facilitated by trained research assistants who ensured consistency in the distribution and were available to address any participant queries. Upon completion of the data collection phase, the gathered responses were carefully reviewed for completeness and consistency.

The collected data were then entered into a statistical software program for analysis. Descriptive statistics, such as frequency counts and weighted means, were calculated to interpret the levels of awareness, acceptability, and alignment of BISU's VMGO as perceived by different stakeholder groups. The results were analyzed to identify strengths and areas needing improvement. Based on the findings, a comprehensive report was compiled, highlighting the overall awareness, acceptability, and congruency of the VMGO. This report was subsequently disseminated to BISU administration and other relevant stakeholders to inform strategic planning and policy-making. Recommendations were provided to enhance the integration of the VMGO into the university's practices and to improve stakeholder engagement. Following the dissemination of the findings, a feedback loop was established to encourage continuous improvement and alignment of BISU's strategic goals with the needs of its stakeholders.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are fundamental in ensuring the integrity and validity of the research process, especially when it involves human participants. This study adhered to the following ethical guidelines to maintain the highest standards of research ethics: Informed Consent, Confidentiality and Anonymity, Data Protection, Respect for Participants.

Results and Discussion

The level of implementation of BISU VMGO is determined by the data gathered from the respondents. The findings of the study revealed that the respondents' level of participation in the VMGO's formulation, dissemination, awareness, and integration in the actual educational practices and activities, including research and extension are generally good. This proved that the respondents are aware of the implementation of the four functions of the university in accordance with its VMGO. The faculty and staff of BISU also agreed that the VMGO is well-disseminated through various means. However, in terms of BISU VMGO profile as rated by the students shows that they still need more opportunities to participate in the review of the school's VMGO.

Table 1. *Level of Awareness of VMGO by the BISU Calape Students*

Students			
Level of Awareness	Mean	Interpretation	
The institution follows a system of formulating the Vision and Mission.	3.61	Highly Aware	
The College follows a system of formulating its goals and the objectives of the program.	3.61	Highly Aware	
The Vision clearly reflects what the institution hopes to become in the future.	3.63	Highly Aware	
The Mission clearly reflects the institutions' legal and educational mandate.	3.60	Highly Aware	
The Goals of the College are consistent with the Mission of the institution.	3.61	Highly Aware	
The Objectives have the expected outcomes in terms of competencies (skills and knowledge), values and other attributes of the graduates.	3.58	Highly Aware	
The Institution/College conducts a review on the statement of the Vision and Mission as well as its goals and program objectives for approval of authorities concerned.	3.54	Highly Aware	
Students are given the opportunity to participate in the formulation, review, and or revision and the implementation of the VMGO.	3.56	Highly Aware	
Variable Mean	3.59	Highly Aware	

Table 1 shows the level of awareness as perceived by the students. Awareness is the extent to which the university community and stakeholders like our students are informed about the VMGO. Based on the results, the students are generally "highly aware" of the vision, mission, goals, and objectives of the university. This infers that the students are well informed about the university's vision, mission, goals, and objectives.

Table 2. *Level of Acceptability and Congruency of VMGO as Perceived by the Students*

Level of Acceptability	Mean	Interpretation	
The VMGO are available on bulletin boards, in catalogs/manuals and in other forms of communication media.	3.54	Fully Observed	
Programs and activities are periodically conducted to disseminate the university VMGO.	3.51	Fully Observed	
Students are conscious and responsive of the BISU VMGO.	3.48	Fully Observed	
Students are given copies, have read, understand, accepted and live out of the school VMGO.	3.48	Fully Observed	
Students actively participate in activities and programs geared toward the VMGO realization.	3.49	Fully Observed	
Students have been provided orientation activities and class discussions for them to familiarize and understand the VMGO of the school.	3.56	Fully Observed	
Variable Mean	3.51	Fully Observed	
Level of Congruency (Instruction)	Mean	Interpretation	
The students have memorized, understand and accepted the university VMGO.	3.21	Great Extent	

The students exhibit good performance in licensure examinations.	3.38	Very Great Extent
Lessons taught in school integrate values reflective of national customs, cultures, and traditions.	3.43	Very Great Extent
Students are given opportunity to participate in the periodic review, assessment, and updating of curriculum.	3.41	Very Great Extent
Graduates are employed in jobs related to their fields of specialization.	3.32	Very Great Extent
Students participate in the implementation of policies on faculty attendance and conduct of instruction.	3.40	Very Great Extent
Students use instructional materials in their subjects in congruent with the VMGO standards.	3.37	Very Great Extent
Curriculum content and design integrate strategies and activities that enable the students to work toward the institution's VMGO.	3.38	Very Great Extent
Periodic assessment and evaluation of students performance is conducted using varied tools.	3.37	Very Great Extent
Variable Mean	3.36	Very Great Extent
<i>Level of Congruency (Research & Extension)</i>		
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Students are compelled to actively engaged in research as part of their course requirement.	3.42	Very Great Extent
Students are encouraged to do quality research outputs that responds to the needs of the local and national communities.	3.43	Very Great Extent
Students are given the opportunity to get involved in the conduct of extension program and activities of the university.	3.43	Very Great Extent
Students are actively involved in the conduct of extension activities in priority areas based on existing needs	3.43	Very Great Extent
Variable Mean	3.43	Very Great Extent
Grand Mean	3.49	Very Great Extent

Table 2 shows the acceptability and congruency of the VMGO as perceived by the students. Acceptability measures how well the VMGO is observed by the stakeholders.

Based on the results, the students generally had “fully observed” the vision, mission, and goals of the university. This means that the VMGO is widely disseminated in various means.

Congruency of the VMGO to its core functions such as instruction, research and extension examines the extent to which the VMGO is aligned to the actual experiences and perceptions of the stakeholders within the university setting. As shown, each implementation criteria have a “very great extent” interpretation from the respondents who rated the study. This infers that

Table 3. Level of Awareness of VMGO as Perceived by the Faculty and Staff

<i>Faculty & Staff</i>		
<i>Level of Awareness</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
The institution follows a system of formulating the Vision and Mission	3.77	Highly Aware
The College follows a system of formulating its goals and the objectives of the program.	3.72	Highly Aware
The Vision clearly reflects what the institution hopes to become in the future.	3.74	Highly Aware
The Mission clearly reflects the institutions' legal and educational mandate.	3.77	Highly Aware
The Goals of the College are consistent with the Mission of the institution.	3.79	Highly Aware
The Objectives have the expected outcomes in terms of competencies (skills and knowledge), values and other attributes of the graduates.	3.85	Highly Aware
The Institution/College conducts a review on the statement of the Vision and Mission as well as its goals and program objectives for approval of authorities concerned.	3.64	Highly Aware
The faculty and staff are given the opportunity to participate in the formulation, review and revision of the VMGO.	3.41	Highly Aware
Variable Mean	3.71	Highly Aware

Table 3 shows the level of awareness as perceived by the faculty and staff. Awareness is the extent to which the university community and stakeholders like our students are informed about the VMGO. Based on the results, the faculty and staff are “highly aware” of the vision, mission, goals, and objectives of the university.

Table 4. Level of Acceptability and Congruency as Perceived by the Faculty and Staff

<i>Level of Acceptability</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
The VMGO are available on bulletin boards, in catalogs/manuals and in other forms of communication media.	3.85	Fully Observed
Programs and activities are periodically conducted to disseminate the university VMGO.	3.62	Fully Observed
The VMGO are crafted and duly approved by the BOR/BOT.	3.85	Fully Observed
Faculty and staff actively participate in the realization of the VMGO as manifested in their competencies of performing their job.	3.67	Fully Observed
A system of dissemination and acceptability of the VMGO is enforced.	3.67	Fully Observed
Variable Mean	3.73	Fully Observed
<i>Level of Congruency (Instruction)</i>		
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
VMGO is integrated and reflected in course functions, syllabus, log frames, lessons, and all the	3.85	Very Great Extent

academic activities of the university.			
The university maintains the standard mandated by the CHED CMO #37	3.82	Very Great Extent	
The curricular content of the diverse course offering responds to the needs of the global community and in line with the recent development and the technical and professional disciplines.	3.74	Very Great Extent	
Integration of values is reflected in the National customs, culture and tradition as evident in the syllabus, log frames, development plans and programs.	3.72	Very Great Extent	
The performance of the university program as reflected in the results of national licensure examination among graduates is highly comparable to the national and international standard.	3.77	Very Great Extent	
The conduct of periodic review assessment and updating of curriculum is participated by the stakeholders.	3.72	Very Great Extent	
Majority of graduates gain employment in jobs related to their field of specialization.	3.46	Very Great Extent	
The institution implements rules and policies on the attendance and performance of the faculty in their respective classes.	3.79	Very Great Extent	
Quality instruction is sustained by requiring the faculty to employ IM, updated syllabi, examination questions in accordance with the university standard of excellence.	3.85	Very Great Extent	
Curricular programs, objectives in each college of the university are designed or formulated in accordance with the university VMGO.	3.82	Very Great Extent	
There is an assessment system of curricular program of the university which evaluates how well the program carries out, the revision and mission of the institution.	3.72	Very Great Extent	
The university/college/department has a research unit manage by competent and capable chairpersons and members.	3.82	Very Great Extent	
The research agenda of the university is in consonance with institutional, regional and national priorities especially those of government agencies.	3.77	Very Great Extent	
Team research is encouraged among faculty as reflected in their participation in national and international colloquium and consortium.	3.77	Very Great Extent	
	Variable Mean	3.76	Very Great Extent
<i>Level of Congruency (Research & Extension)</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
The faculty are encouraged to do quality research outputs that responds to the needs of the local and national communities.	3.74	Very Great Extent	
The faculty is actively engaged in research as part of the four fold functions, either in group or individual research endeavors.	3.44	Very Great Extent	
Every faculty is involved in the conduct of extension programs and activities in line with their expertise or field specialization.	3.46	Very Great Extent	
Evaluation of extension program is conducted periodically as reflected in extension meetings and evaluation results.	3.49	Very Great Extent	
	Variable Mean	3.53	Very Great Extent
	Grand Mean	3.69	Very Great Extent

Table 4 shows the level of acceptability and congruency as perceived by the faculty and staff. As shown, they generally have “fully observed” the university’s vision, mission, goals, and objectives. In terms of congruency, the faculty and staff perceived a “very great extent” interpretation of the criteria provided.

Table 5. *Level of Awareness as Perceived by the External Stakeholders*

<i>External Stakeholders</i>		
<i>Level of Awareness</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
The institution follows a system of formulating the Vision and Mission.	3.69	Highly Aware
The College follows a system of formulating its goals and the objectives of the program.	3.62	Highly Aware
The Vision clearly reflects what the institution hopes to become in the future.	3.62	Highly Aware
The Mission clearly reflects the institutions’ legal and educational mandate.	3.62	Highly Aware
The Goals of the College are consistent with the Mission of the institution.	3.62	Highly Aware
The Objectives have the expected outcomes in terms of competencies (skills and knowledge), values and other attributes of the graduates.	3.62	Highly Aware
The Institution/College conducts a review on the statement of the Vision and Mission as well as its goals and program objectives for approval of authorities concerned.	3.77	Highly Aware
The cooperating agencies, local and international linkages, alumni, industry representatives and other concerned organizations/groups in the community are given opportunity to participate in the formulation, review and or revision of the VMGO.	3.62	Highly Aware
	Variable Mean	3.65
		Highly Aware

Table 5 shows the level of awareness as perceived by external stakeholders. Based on the results, external stakeholders are “highly aware” of the vision, mission, goals, and objectives of the university.

Table 6 shows the level of acceptability and congruency as perceived by the university’s external stakeholders. As shown, they generally have “fully observed” the university’s vision, mission, goals, and objectives. In terms of congruency, they perceived a “very great extent” interpretation of the criteria provided.

Table 6. *Level of Acceptability and Congruency as Perceived by the External Stakeholders*

<i>Level of Acceptability</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
The VMGO are available on bulletin boards, in catalogs/manuals and in other forms of communication media.	3.69	Fully Observed
Programs and activities such as community visits and giving out of leaflets and brochures are periodically conducted to disseminate the university VMGO.	3.38	Fully Observed
BISU VMGO is anchored on the community needs and demand.	3.46	Fully Observed
The community is conscious and responsive of the BISU VMGO.	3.54	Fully Observed
The community is actively participating in activities and programs geared towards the VMGO realization.	3.46	Fully Observed
Variable Mean	3.51	Fully Observed
<i>Level of Congruency(Instruction)</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Lessons and values learned in school are manifested by the graduates in their respective places and fields.	3.54	Very Great Extent
Students are job-ready and highly employable.	3.54	Very Great Extent
Graduates are easily employed in jobs related to their field of specialization.	3.46	Very Great Extent
The university offers priority courses and disciplines that are congruent and responsive to the needs of the community and the partner industries.	3.46	Very Great Extent
The university has produced topnotchers and placers in licensure examinations and has been acclaimed as top-performing school of the country.	3.62	Very Great Extent
Variable Mean	3.52	Very Great Extent
<i>Level of Congruency (Research & Extension)</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
The Research program is conducted in the community based on the existing research agenda of the community.	3.46	Very Great Extent
The community has been involved in the research activities of the university.	3.38	Very Great Extent
The community has been coordinating with the university in extension projects which are meant to achieve sustainable development in specific fields.	3.38	Very Great Extent
The university maintains cooperation with the local and national government units in the implementation of its research and extension agenda.	3.46	Very Great Extent
The university has international linkages in benchmarking its instruction, research and extension pursuits.	3.46	Very Great Extent
The university has consistently developed and managed production made it a self-sustaining higher education provider.	3.46	Very Great Extent
Variable Mean	3.43	Very Great Extent
Grand Mean	3.54	Very Great Extent

Conclusions

The study concludes that BISU's VMGO is effectively observed and implemented, particularly in areas related to awareness and dissemination. However, increasing student participation in the formulation and revision processes is necessary to enhance the relevance and alignment of the VMGO with stakeholder expectations.

To maximize the effectiveness of BISU's VMGO, the study recommends the following:

Encourage more student involvement in the review and revision of the VMGO to ensure that it reflects their needs and aspirations.

Strengthen Integration: Further integrate the VMGO into the educational practices and activities of the university to promote a shared vision and collective commitment.

Continuous Evaluation: Implement regular assessments of stakeholder awareness, acceptability, and congruency to monitor the effectiveness of VMGO communication and implementation strategies.

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